

[Yosef Rozsansky](#) is positive and passionate about nutrition and healthy living! This registered dietitian is known for his comprehensive approach that encompasses physical, mental and spiritual well-being. You can count on Yosef Rozsansky for sound professional expertise and practical ideas to make good nutrition easier. You can also count on him to find a way to balance in your favorite fun foods.

Yosef Rozsansky started his nutrition career more than fifteen years ago. Today, he is a well-respected nutritionist providing individual counselling and group sessions in weight management and how to manage healthy blood sugars. Rozsansky also provides a wide variety of nutrition counselling services in preventative health, chronic disease, emotional eating and weight management education. Over his career she has developed skills and a special interest in working collaboratively with psychologists and physicians regarding disordered eating, anorexia, bulimia and binge eating disorder recovery.

Yosef Rozsansky completed his Bachelor of Science in Nutrition at the University of Wisconsin-Madison and Master of Science degree in Applied Physiology and Nutrition from Teachers College, Columbia University.